

AN OVERVIEW ON THE SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW FOR THE LEGAL RESEARCH

—Sidhartha Sekhar Dash*

ABSTRACT

Successful research needs a systematic and methodological approach. It is to know the existing work systematically to identify the gaps for further exploration and to make an addition to the existing knowledge of legal studies. Introduction of the Systematic Literature Review in the works of Legal discipline shall make the works more scientific and methodological. The paper offers an overview of the Systematic Literature Review to the legal scholars with further readings on the area.

Keywords: Literature Review, SLR., Legal Research, Systematic Literature Review, Search String.

INTRODUCTION

A legal scholar when faces any question to do research or attempts to prepare a manuscript, the important research skill among others is to conduct the review of literature in a fair and organised way. The literature review is the foundation of academic research. The literature review summarises the body of literature that is relevant to the article. It is a methodological approach where existing literature is collected and further those are analysed to answer a specific question. If one ranks the order of deficiencies in any cited manuscript, the literature review section of a paper remains among the top five causes of rejection of a paper¹. To address this, the most robust, organised and stream-

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¹ McKercher, B., Law, R., et. al., *Why Referees Reject Manuscripts*. JOURNAL OF HOSPITALITY & TOURISM RESEARCH, 31(4), 455-470 (2007), <https://doi.org/10.1177/1096348007302355>

lined method of approaching the review of research works is the *systematic literature review or SLR*.

WHAT IS SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

A systematic literature review, Cochrane says, attempts "to identify, appraise and synthesize all the empirical evidence that meets pre-specified eligibility criteria to answer a given research question"². "Systematic literature reviews originated in medicine and are linked to evidence based practice"³.

"A successful review involves three major stages: planning the review, conducting the review, and reporting the review."⁴ The systematic literature review answers all the descriptions of these stages. It is a type of literature review that collects and critically analyzes multiple research studies or papers through a systematic process. The purpose of this type of Literature Review is to provide an exhaustive summary of the available literature relevant to a research question.

It is different to the traditional authoritative review, as it needs identification of the current literature, the limitation of the literature, its quality and potential. The authoritative or opinionated review helps a researcher to approach poorly conducted research but this method allows imprecise and unreliable presentation of evidence. This can be overcome if the study design is conducted with meticulous planning and execution. The systematic literature review can be used in legal research in many fruitful ways like demonstrating the legal or policy impact and outline crime prevention. This can also help to point research gaps, identify potential areas for future research, outline crime prevention strategies and the extent to which a problem is understood.

STEPS OF CONDUCTING SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

To conduct a systematic literature review a researcher need to set guidelines before the review that helps him to reduce down the focus of the project.

(According to the study in the field of hospitality and tourism, content analysis of 373 referees' reports of manuscripts submitted to 35 journals where rejection or major revision was recommended, 50.9 % of the manuscript were rejected on the literature review section of a paper).

² McKercher, B., Law, R., et. al., *Why Referees Reject Manuscripts*. JOURNAL OF HOSPITALITY & TOURISM RESEARCH, 31(4), 455-470. (2007), <https://doi.org/10.1177/1096348007302355>.
³ *Library Guides: Literature Review: Systematic Literature Reviews* (2016). <https://libguides.csu.edu.au/review/Systematic>.
⁴ Kitchenham, Barbara & Stuart Charters, *Systematic Literature Reviews in Software Engineering*, KEELE UNIVERSITY AND DURHAM UNIVERSITY, EBSE-001 (2007), <https://userpages.uni-koblenz.de/~laemmel/esecourse/slides/slr.pdf>.

This makes the research methodology transparent and replicable⁵. Pittway (2008) "outlines seven key principles behind systematic literature reviews. Those are, Transparency, Clarity, Integration, Focus, Equality, Accessibility, and Coverage⁶". During the systematic literature review, a researcher can use different kinds of literature like Legislative Acts, Cases laws, law commission reports, journal and newspaper articles, NGO Reports, parliamentary discussions, Policy decisions, and other governmental reports.

A. Putting Down the Rules or Protocol

The researcher must pen down the rules for the systematic literature review and do a daily track of his research activities. This shall help him to make a timeline of his project, keep track of the decision-making process.

B. Research Question

"Literature reviews are research inquiries, and all research inquiries should be guided by research questions. Research questions, therefore, drive the entire literature review process"⁷. After penning down the rules for the systematic literature review, the researcher should determine his research question. This helps to shape what literature is to be included and what excluded. "While conducting the review, unforeseeable problems may arise that requires modifications to the research question and/or review protocol. An often-encountered problem is that the research question was too broad and the researchers need to narrow down the topic and adjust the inclusion criterion⁸". The researcher should have clear in his frame of mind the appropriate information needed to answer his research question. Additionally, the researcher can also explain as to why the criteria were selected.

C. Knowing what to search for

This is one of the important steps for conducting the systematic literature review. When a legal researcher tries to search in any specific domain of study, say revenue laws, he may encounter thousands of works on the search site. This is known as putting suitable *search-string*. "A suitable *search-string* for a

⁵ Reshchikov, A. & van Achterberg K., *Review of the Genus Metopheltes Uchida, 1932 (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae) with Description of a New Species from Vietnam*. 2 BIODIVERSITY DATA JOURNAL. (2014), <https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.2.e1061>.

⁶ *Library Guides: Literature Review: Systematic Literature Reviews* (2016). <https://libguides.csu.edu.au/review/Systematic>.

⁷ Irimia R. & Gottschling M., *Taxonomic Revision of Rochefortia Sw. (Ehretiaceae, Boraginales)*. BIODIVERSITY DATA JOURNAL 4: e7720. (2016), <https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.4.e7720>.

⁸ Xiao, Yu & Maria Watson, *Guidance on Conducting a Systematic Literature Review*, JOURNAL OF PLANNING EDUCATION AND RESEARCH. (2017), <https://doi.org/10.1177/0739456X17723971>.

search engine is specific, inclusive and aware of the variability in terminology/reporting"⁹. Since most of the search site's engine delivers end-results by algorithmic assessments search or keywords, to weed out published manuscripts of other paradigms the researcher should use *well thought out* keywords/ search strings. The researcher must be consistent with his search string. Moreover, he must record the search string as this is a requirement to state in the manuscript. The researcher can use the automatic searches in the search engine to narrow down the search further, like, years of publication of the judgements, specific HC or only the SC. This depends upon the inclusion or the exclusion criteria of the researcher. The specifics of the search depend upon the search engine used.

D. Where to search

There are various search engines in the legal field. Say for example a person is searching Indian case laws on a subject. He can opt for a non-paid and free search engine like Indiakanon.org, Researchgate, Mendeley and SSRN. Multiple search engines should be used by a researcher in the systematic review. Also for paid software like HeinOnline, Manupatra, for qualitative data analysis ATLAS.ti. It all depends upon the preference of the researcher and the subject matter of the work.

After this the researcher is to manage and interpret the findings according to the objective of the research. And finally, the researcher is to structure his review in order to find the research gap, if any.

SUGGESTED BOOKS

A few Suggested pieces of literature on the Systematic Literature Review are reflected here for the researchers.

1. Fink, A. (2014). *Conducting Research Literature Reviews: From the Internet to Paper*. Los Angeles, CA: SAGE.
2. Hagen-Zanker, J. & Mallet, R. (2013). *How to do a Rigorous, Evidence Focused Literature Review in International Development: A Guidance Note*. Working paper Overseas Direct Investment.
3. Oliver, S., & Sutcliffe, K. (2012). *Describing and analysing studies*. Gough, D. A. & Oliver, S. In *An Introduction to Systematic Reviews*. London, UK. SAGE.
4. Pittaway, L. (2008). *Systematic Literature Reviews*. Thorpe, R. & Holt, R. In *The Sage Dictionary of Qualitative Management Research*. London, UK. SAGE.
5. Siddaway, A. (2014). *What Is a Systematic*

⁹ *How to Write a Systematic Literature Review: A Guide for Medical Students (n.d.)*. Cardiff.ac.uk. Retrieved Sept. 7, 2022, from <https://sites.cardiff.ac.uk/curesmed/files/2014/10/NSAMR-Systematic-Review.pdf>.

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(new) light into the

The next article by **Dash** is a pragmatic but noteworthy contribution that should have appeal to students and young scholars as the author discusses how to effectively conduct a literature review for legal research. Again, the article should/could arguably be recommended to any aspiring law student since learning how to write a peer reviewed article, let alone engage in sound legal research is an acquired skill that usually requires practice. In particular, the article addresses a fundamental element of how to prepare a scholarly paper.

In the following article, **Shahi** introduces the reader to a new term that has

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